

Milestone: M5.1 Country exchange visits concluded

Lead Participant:

INSA

Author:

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Due:

30 Sep 2021

Date Of Completion:

15 Sep 2021

Means of Verification

UK Country Exchange Visit

- [Minutes](#); [Slides](#); [Recordings](#)

Estonian Country Exchange Visit

- [Minutes](#); [Slides](#); [Recordings](#)

Finnish Country Exchange Visit

- [Minutes](#); [Slides](#); [Recordings](#)

Milestone Delayed (if yes, please explain)

No

Project participants & others

- WP5 Co-leads: Astrid Vicente (INSA), Serena Scollen (ELIXIR)
- Contributing Members (from): INSA, ELIXIR, U Tartu, Finnish Ministry of Social Affairs and Health, Genomics England, ISCIII, Tervise Arengu Instituut
- 34 External Speakers & Panelists (see minutes)
- Number of participants (on average per visit):
 - UK visit - 67 ; Estonia Visit - 95; Finland Visit - 80.

Next action steps

- To create a report summarising the key discussion points from each country visit, including the presentations from the participating Member State countries on national genomic programs.
- To create and disseminate policy briefs targeted to policymakers, healthcare professionals, and other relevant individuals within healthcare, outlining key factors for the adoption of genomics by healthcare systems.

B1MG has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation programme under grant agreement No 951724